

LANGUAGE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS FORMATION OF LEARNING ABILITIES INNOVATIVE METHODS

Saminjonova Zuxraxon Xusanboy qizi

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Department of English Language and literature

4nd year bachelor student

E-mail: saminjonovazuxraxon@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article discusses innovative ways to shape the language skills of primary school students and the role and importance of dictionaries in this process.

Keywords. Language teaching, elementary school, vocabulary, innovative methods, communication, student psyche.

The only way to introduce more and more innovative technologies into the educational process is to improve scientific, methodological and methodological education at all levels of the education system. The Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis emphasizes the need to "improve school curricula on the basis¹³ of advanced foreign experience, revise teaching loads and subjects, bring them into line with international standards, improve the quality of textbooks and literature." These words impose a great responsibility on all teachers in our country, especially young teachers.

Currently, a number of positive measures are being taken in the country to educate, train, educate the younger generation, to approach modern information technologies. Interest in the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in education is growing. At each stage of world civilization, the criteria and requirements for the teacher's personality, professional skills and abilities were considered, and specific aspects of the educational process were studied. Looking at different periods of society's development, the teacher's personality and requirements were developed. The great scholar Mahmudhoja Behbudi said, "I bequeath to you. Wipe the heads of teachers who work

¹³ Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. Uza, January 25, 2020.

for education! Help with education! Do not leave the children of Turkestan without knowledge! If you work, do it with the community! ” he says.

In accordance with the pace of globalization, the demand for teaching and learning foreign languages in our country is very high. The rising generation must know a language in order to be born and communicate with the world. It is important to develop oral and written speech and teach communication to students learning English. The main task of teaching and learning native and foreign languages in educational institutions is to form students' language-specific communicative competencies.¹⁴ Of course, a student must love and know his native language well before learning any foreign language. It is clear that the extensive use of dictionaries to develop the written and oral speech of the younger generation in the process of motivating them to learn English will have positive results. The role and importance of dictionaries in this regard is incomparable.

The content of vocabulary enrichment in students consists of thematic and lexical-semantic groups of words. Typically, representatives of two languages rely on the help of dictionaries that combine both languages to communicate with each other. It is clear that dictionaries are an important factor in further developing students' language learning skills. Assignments such as comparing texts studied can be given in the process of developing students' vocabulary. Students' vocabulary is enriched by studying terms from different fields and analyzing their interpretations.

In the age of modern information technology, not only traditional printed dictionaries, but also electronic dictionaries are developing. This, of course, gives the learner a lot of opportunities and ease. First of all, it saves the learner time in the process of searching for a word he does not know in the dictionary, but also allows him to learn the pronunciation of the word at the same time. Experience has shown that the more vocabulary a student has, the more easily he or she can engage in oral and written communication between people.

If the teacher uses the necessary modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies in the classroom, it will increase the interest of students, expand the scope of knowledge. It is necessary for language learners to determine which speech is best formed, to further develop this skill and to form other weaker aspects of the student using this skill. To achieve this goal, the use of the following recommendations will give positive results:

- organization of various intellectual games that interest students during the lessons;

¹⁴ Mahmudhoja Behbudi. Selected works. "Spirituality", T.1995. 254-b.

- Introduce interesting texts on various topics, translate them and write dictation in order to develop the ability to work with dictionaries during the lesson;
- use of TV and radio materials on listening comprehension and word memorization;
- use of logical and mental word games related to dictionaries in the classroom;
- Organize discussions and debates on various topics of interest to students using the vocabulary;

Today in our country serious attention is paid to the study and teaching of foreign languages. The training of independent-minded, open-minded, mature professionals who can contribute to the future development through the perfect teaching of foreign languages should become the main goal of every foreign language teacher.

An innovative teaching method is a system of teacher-centered activities aimed at organizing the student's learning activities and achieving the objectives of the lesson. The innovative teaching method not only reveals the content of teaching, but also reflects the personality of the teacher and the student, the form of communication between them. These tasks are the result of the features of the new education system, as well as the process of radical reforms in all spheres of society.

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